

PAM 43.661 frag. 81 = 4Q38a (4QDeut^{k2})
and Identification of 4Q38a frag. 9

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1. PAM 43.661 frag. 81

The editors of DJD 33 correctly transcribed PAM 43.661 frag. 81 as]◦ ארש[and commented that “forms of ארש consisting of or ending in these three letters are rare in the Bible (Deut 20:7; 28:30), and do not appear in the known non-biblical Qumran texts” (p. 15). Yet, they they did not pursue the possibility that this fragment, which had been assigned to plates with unidentified fragments, could belong to one of the Deuteronomy manuscripts.

The fragments fits in the gap of 4Q38a (4QDeut^{k2}) frag. 2 line 3 (see publication in DJD 14, p. 101 and Pl. XXV). The right and bottom edge of PAM 43.661 frag. 81 joins materially to 4Q38a frag. 2, which itself is a conglomerate of joined pieces. One can therefore now read line 4Q38a frags. 2-3 line 2 as follows:

אשר ארש א[ש]ה ולוא] לקחה 2

2. 4Q38a frag. 9 (IAA Plate 1090, Frag 10)

The DJD 14 editor failed to identify the fragment due to the misinterpretation of the traces of line 2, which show, before the *kap*, the head of a *yod* as well as the left part of a basestroke. The fragment fits perfectly to the right side of 4Q38a frag. 4 in lines 2-3 (and preserves the tip of *lamed* of line 4). The traces visible on frag. 9 may be identified as follows

]כָּה[

]פִּיכָה[

]לָ[

Joined to the right of 4Q38k frag. 4 lines 2-4 one can now read:

שפתי]כָּה תשמו]ר 2

ב]פִּיכָה כא] תבוא 3

וא]ל כליכה] לוא 4

References:

- DJD 14 Eugene Ulrich et al., *Qumran Cave 4, IX: Deuteronomy, Joshua, Judges, Kings*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 14 (Oxford: Clarendon, 1995)
- DJD 33 Dana Pike and Andrew Skinner, *Qumran Cave 4, XXIII: Unidentified Fragments*, Discoveries in the Judaean Desert 33 (Oxford: Clarendon, 2001)
- IAA Israel Antiquities Authority (used for reference to Plate numbers with scrolls fragments). Fragment numbers are those given by the IAA in The Leon Levy Dead Sea Scrolls Digital Library, deadseascrolls.org.il
- PAM Palestine Archaeological Museum (used for references to PAM photographs).